

INTRAVASCULAR PLATELET ACTIVATION IN WOMEN WITH MISSION OF PREGNANCY WITH AND WITHOUT HYPERHOMOCYSTEINEMIA

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Relevance: Miscarriage is currently defined as the recurring cessation of pregnancy. There are many syndromes associated with recurrent miscarriage: anatomical abnormalities, hormonal disorders, chromosomal defects, disorders in the state of the blood coagulation system.

Recently, it has been proven that there is a close the relationship between the development of the morphofunctional state of the body and the rheological properties of blood, largely due to the level of platelet activity. At the same time, changes in the functional properties of platelets often play a significant role in the initiation and progression of thrombus formation. From this point of view, the study of the state of the platelet link of the hemostasis system and the content of homocysteine in the blood of patients with miscarriage is of considerable interest, since parallel violations in these links of the hemocoagulation mechanism are an additional factor provoking the development of thrombosis.

Material and research methods: We examined 78 women aged 18 to 26 years, 24 of whom (Group 1) were patients with a miscarriage, who received folic acid preparations and B vitamins, in order to correct hyperhomocysteinemia and maintained their pregnancy. In 54 patients (Group 2) with aborted pregnancy. The gestational age of women in the control, first and second groups was 8.27 ± 1.60 , 7.50 ± 2.19 , 7.60 ± 2.40 weeks, respectively. The control group consisted of 18 patients with normal gestational process.

Conclusions: In women with miscarriage, changes in the metabolism of homocysteine and an increase in the aggregation activity of platelets were revealed, which indicate their close relationship, therefore, early detection of hyperhomocysteinemia (upon admission of patients to the clinic), timely conduct of appropriate therapy aimed at reducing the content of homocysteine, as well as the use of a complex of additional antithrombotic measures will be an important link in the system of prevention of miscarriage.

Literature:

1. Andrianova M. Yu., Roitman E. V., Isaeva A. M., Kolesnikova I. M., Nureev M. V. Pathogenetic and clinical substantiation of the complex prevention of hyperhomocysteinemia // Archives of Internal Medicine. 2014. No. 4.-C 51-56
2. Baranova, E.I. Clinical significance of homocysteinemia (literature review) / E.I. Baranova, O.O. Bolshakova // Arterial hypertension. - 2004. - T. 10, No. 1. - S. 12-18.
3. Butenko A. V. Homocysteine: influence on biochemical processes in the human body // Young scientist. - 2016. - No. 1. — S. 78-82.
4. Genetic disorders of the coagulation cascade and homocysteine metabolism in the genesis of cerebral thrombosis / O. V. Sirotkina, Yu. V. Cherkas, A. V. Merkulova et al. // Med. academic journal. 2004. -T. 4, No. 4. - S. 23-28.
5. Kanevskaya, N.P. Platelet-vascular system of hemostasis in metabolic disorders in women with arterial hypertension: Abstract of the thesis. dis. . cand. honey. Sciences. - Orenburg, 2003. - 24 p.
6. Kozlova, T.V. Hyperhomocysteinemia as a clinical manifestation of the risk of thrombosis / T.V. Kozlova // Wedge, medicine. 2005. - No. 2. - S. 9-11.
7. Clinical aspects of hypercysteinemia: monograph / ed. V.A. Snezhitsky, V.M. Pyrochkina [i dr.]. - GrGMU, 2011. - 292 p.
8. Makarenko, M.V. Management of pregnant women with fetal growth retardation syndrome on the background of thrombophilia and hyperhomocysteinemia / M.V. Makarenko // Family medicine. - 2014. - No. 3 (53). - S. 155.
9. Naumov, A.V. Homocysteine in the pathogenesis of microcirculatory and thrombotic complications / A.V. Naumov, T.N. Grinevich, V.M. Naidina // Thrombosis, hemostasis and rheology. - 2012. - T. 49, No. 4 - S. 9-19.
10. The level of homocysteine and indicators of platelet aggregation in patients with impaired cerebral circulation / Z. Sabaliauskiene, P. Gribauskas, V. Gaigalaite [et al.] // Therapeutic archive. - 2013. - T. 85, No. 3. - S. 75-79.
11. Shilova, A.N. Thromboembolism of the pulmonary arteries against the background of hyperhomocysteinemia / A.N. Shilova, A.A. Karpenko, Yu.E. Klevanets // Angiology and vascular surgery. - 2015. - V. 21, No. 1. - S. 25-28.
12. Shevchenko, O.P. Homocysteine is a new risk factor for atherosclerosis and thrombosis / O.P. Shevchenko // Klin. lab. diagnostics. - 2004. - No. 10. - S. 25-31.

13. Shitikova, A.S. Method for determining intravascular platelet activation and its significance in clinical practice / A.S. Shitikova, L.R. Tarkovskaya, V.D. Kargin // Klin. lab. diagnostics. 1997. - No. 2. - S. 23-25.
14. Perla-Kajan J., Twardowski T., and Jakubowski H. Mechanisms of homocysteine toxicity in humans // Amino Acids (2007) 32: 561–572
15. Yilmaz N. Relationship between paraoxonase and homocysteine: crossroads of oxidative diseases // Arch Med Sci 1, February / 2012. P. 138–153.

